

Sketch of a path integral approach for bound states in quantum field theory

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Abstract

I outline how existing many-particle techniques might be used for a path integral approach to the bound state problem in quantum field theory. The approach allows deriving an action for composite particles from the single particle theories and their interactions. The saddle point equation of this theory is a non-linear analog of the Bethe-Salpeter equation. I shortly discuss the relationship of non-linearity with the condensation of the compound particles.

The relativistic two-body problem was considered in 1951 by Bethe and Salpeter (BS) [1, 2] and put on a sound theoretical basis by Gell-Mann and Low [3]. The central result is the famous Bethe-Salpeter-equation (BSE), which is the basis for treating bound states in quantum field theory.

Approaching this problem using the path integral formalism is interesting for two reasons. Firstly, it allows deriving an action for the composite system, i.e., to go beyond an equation of motion. Secondly, there might be non-trivial saddle points.

Here, I will focus on the generic structure of the equations and only consider simple examples to illustrate the technique. For the sake of a clear presentation I will make a few simplifications. Although the same starting point technically allows for three and more particles, I will give detailed steps only for pairs of particles. Further simplifications (to be described below) will only yield the BSE in ladder approximation, but there seems to be no fundamental restrictions for a more general treatment.

The main results are a derived action for the composite particle and a derived non-linear analog of the BSE. The non-linearity in the resulting equation can be understood using the example of BCS theory of superconductivity. A few observations regarding the structure of the equations will be discussed, in particular the resulting interaction terms.

Outline of the method. Consider a field theory for interacting particles, no matter if self-interacting or with interactions between different types of particles. To build composites, we adopt a method used in the context of electron systems with random impurities [4]. This technique identifies pairs of fields with a new field. We use it to identify two or more particles with a composite field by introducing a functional delta function

$$1 = \int \mathcal{D}Q \delta[Q_{j_1, \dots, j_N} - \rho_{j_1, \dots, j_N} \psi_{j_1} \cdots \psi_{j_N}] \quad (1)$$

into the path integral of a partition function $Z = \int \mathcal{D}\psi^\dagger \mathcal{D}\psi \exp(iS)$. Here, ψ shall represent the collection of fields ψ_j . An appropriate choice of time contour and $\hbar = 1$ are understood. The fields ψ_j may be fermions or bosons and the appropriate fields and boundary conditions have to be used (i.e., Grassmann fields in the case of fermions). The pre-factors ρ_{j_1, \dots, j_N} can be seen as normalization constants, but can also be used to start from convenient linear combinations. (For example, if a singlet-triplet representation is desired from the start.) The identification Eq. (1) can be used for more than two particles, but for simplicity I will only consider pairs below.¹

For the sake of simplicity, I will use a few approximations, neither of which is a fundamental restriction. I will assume that gauge interactions (if involved) can be integrated out after gauge fixing. In non-abelian gauge theories this is an approximation. I will omit any further radiative corrections to the resulting four-fermion interaction, but it is technically possible to carry them along. Thirdly, as already mentioned, I will only consider bound states of pairs of particles in the following. Binding three particles invokes the problems of three-body problems and will not be discussed here. However, binding a third particle to a tightly bound pair could be achieved by applying the pair technique twice.

The starting point for pairs is an action of the form $S = S_m + S_{\text{int}}$ with single particle actions summed up into

$$S_m = \sum_{j=1}^2 \int dx \psi_j^\dagger(x) G_j^{-1}(x) \psi_j(x) \quad (2)$$

with $x = (\mathbf{x}, t)$ and an interaction of the form

$$S_{\text{int}} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j, j'=1}^2 \int dx dx' \psi_j^\dagger(x) \psi_{j'}^\dagger(x') V_{jj'}(x-x') \psi_{j'}(x') \psi_j(x), \quad (3)$$

¹It should be mentioned that pairs can also be treated by Hubbard-Stratonovich transformation. The latter is less general, but often the usefulness of both methods depends in the same way on the treatment of the fourth order interaction.

In S_m , the inverse Green functions $G_j^{-1}(x)$ are differential operators (e.g., $i\partial_t - H_j$ with Hamilton operator H_j). For Dirac fermions (as in the original Bethe-Salpeter setting) use $\bar{\psi} = \psi^\dagger \gamma^0$ and the operator $i\gamma_j^\mu \partial_\mu^{(j)} - m_j$ with $\partial_\mu^{(j)}$ denoting the derivative with respect to x^μ for particle j).

In the first step towards a bound state field theory apply Eq. (1) for two particles. We introduce new fields Q via $\delta[Q(x, x') - \rho\psi_1(x)\psi_2(x')]$. If ψ_j and ψ_j^\dagger are independent, introduce a second independent field Q^\dagger . The normalization constants ρ can typically be set to 1 for pairs of distinguishable particles and $1/\sqrt{2}$ if we couple identical particles.

With the introduction of $Q(x, x')$, involving two time arguments I follow Bethe and Salpeter, who did so to achieve a relativistically covariant theory. The limit of instantaneous interactions can be treated with a single time argument in the BSE [5]. In this case, but in particular for non-relativistic problems we can as well work with a single time argument, by coupling $\delta[Q(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}', t) - \rho\psi_1(\mathbf{x}, t)\psi_2(\mathbf{x}', t)]$ to avoid problems related to two time arguments.

As described above, we insert an integral over a delta functional into the partition function. The delta functional can be represented by the functional integral (for a charged field)

$$\delta[Q] \propto \int \mathcal{D}\Lambda^\dagger \exp(i\Lambda^\dagger Q) , \quad (4)$$

which can be understood in analogy to Fourier transform or a Lagrange multiplier [4]. If Q^\dagger is an independent field, then we have to introduce both Λ and Λ^\dagger accordingly. These fields have two space and time arguments, e.g., $\Lambda = \Lambda(x, x')$. The special case considered here could also be treated using the less general Hubbard-Stratonovich transformation. In the following formulas I assume representatively independent fields Q and Q^\dagger .² The transformed action (re-named S_m after absorbing normalization factors into the functional integral measures) then reads

$$\begin{aligned} S_m &= \text{Tr} \left\{ \psi_1^\dagger G_1^{-1} \psi_1 + \psi_2^\dagger G_2^{-1} \psi_2 \right\} + \text{Tr} \rho \psi_1^T \Lambda^\dagger \psi_2 \\ &+ \text{Tr} \rho^* \psi_2^\dagger \Lambda \psi_1^* + \text{Tr} \left\{ \Lambda^\dagger Q + Q^\dagger \Lambda \right\} . \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

²If the components have opposite charge of equal size, the composite is neutral in the leading order of a multipole expansion. In a 'tight binding' limit one would expect a real field description to be possible. However, there can be dipole and higher order fluctuations, such that it is not necessary that the composite field has to be real.

The trace symbol 'Tr' again includes integrations over x arguments. The interaction part of the action with the appropriate choice for ρ reads

$$S_{\text{int}} = -\text{Tr} \left\{ Q^\dagger(x, x') V(x - x') Q(x, x') \right\} . \quad (6)$$

The complete action is quadratic in the single particle fields, such that the latter can be integrated out. The term $\psi_1^\dagger \Lambda^\dagger \psi_2$ and its conjugate require some care. One approach is to perform the integration over one particle field first and then the other. Another way is to arrange the Green functions and the coupling to Λ into a matrix.

The result of integrating out the single particle fields is an action

$$S_{\text{eff}} = -\text{Tr} Q^\dagger V Q + \text{Tr} \{ \Lambda^\dagger Q + Q^\dagger \Lambda \} \mp i \text{Tr} \ln \{ \mathbb{1} - \Lambda^\dagger G_1 \Lambda G_2 \} \quad (7)$$

for pairs of distinguishable particles. For pairs of identical particles, the last term reads $\mp(i/2) \text{Tr} \ln \{ \mathbb{1} - 2\Lambda^\dagger G_1 \Lambda G_2 \}$ instead. The sign in front of the logarithmic term is minus if both particles are fermions and plus otherwise. One of the Green functions may arise as a 'hole' Green function, as the examples below will show.

Let us now consider the saddle point approximation. Take the first order functional derivatives and require that they vanish,

$$\begin{aligned} -V Q_{\text{SP}} + \Lambda_{\text{SP}} &= 0 , \\ \text{Tr}' G_1 \left(\mathbb{1} - \Lambda_{\text{SP}} G_2 \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger G_1 \right)^{-1} \Lambda_{\text{SP}} G_2 + Q_{\text{SP}} &= 0 . \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

(There are also the dependent and therefore equivalent Hermitian conjugated counterparts.) The trace symbol with a prime is a shorthand notation for the integration over all silent variables and indices and is not a full trace in the strict sense. In this set of saddle point equations one can recognize the structure of the BSE in integral form. But in order to see the relationship with the BSE more clearly, we can bring (8) into a differential form. By applying the inverse Green functions on both sides of the second equation, we obtain

$$G_1^{-1} Q_{\text{SP}} G_2^{-1} = -\text{Tr}' \left(\mathbb{1} - \Lambda_{\text{SP}} G_2 \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger G_1 \right)^{-1} V Q_{\text{SP}} \quad (9)$$

with $\Lambda_{\text{SP}} = V Q_{\text{SP}}$. We may pass from a matrix representation of Q to a n -tuple representation using the tensor product,

$$G_1^{-1} G_2^{-1} Q_{\text{SP}}(x_1, x_2) = - \int dx_3 dx_4 K[\Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger, \Lambda_{\text{SP}}](x_1, x_2; x_3, x_4) Q_{\text{SP}}(x_3, x_4) .$$

This has the shape of the BSE [2, 6]; however, the equation is non-linear, which is reflected by the fact that the kernel

$$K = -\text{Tr}' \left(\mathbb{1} - \Lambda_{\text{SP}} G_2 \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger G_1 \right)^{-1} V \quad (10)$$

depends on the fields themselves in a non-linear way. In the limit of vanishing Λ fields in the expression for K , we obtain the BSE in ladder approximation, which is the desired outcome. In addition, there may be non-trivial saddle points, including such with spatially uniform finite expectation values. This opens up the possibility for condensates, of which a well-known example is superconductivity. This will be considered in more detail below.

Beyond this saddle point approximation, we can expand the theory in quadratic order. This should yield an effective low energy free particle action for the bound state. For the expansion define $Q = Q_{\text{SP}} + q$, $\Lambda = \Lambda_{\text{SP}} + \lambda$. The result of this expansion is

$$S_2 = \text{Tr} \left[-q^\dagger V q + \lambda^\dagger q + q^\dagger \lambda + \boldsymbol{\lambda}^\dagger \mathcal{G}_0 \boldsymbol{\lambda} \right], \quad (11)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\lambda} = (\lambda, \lambda^\dagger)^T$. The kernel \mathcal{G}_0 follows from second order derivatives of the action.³ There are various options to proceed. For example, we can integrate out either q or λ . Choosing to integrate out λ , the result is a Gaussian action for the bound system

$$S_{2,\text{eff}}[q^\dagger, q] = \text{Tr} \left\{ \mathbf{q}^\dagger \mathcal{G}^{-1} \mathbf{q} \right\} \quad (13)$$

with $\mathcal{G}^{-1} = \mathcal{G}_0^{-1} - V \mathbb{1}$ and $\mathbf{q} = (q, q^\dagger)^T$. In some cases it might be desirable to diagonalize (similar to a Bogoliubov transformation).

Why is the second order expansion interesting? This is because it yields a free particle action in which the inner degrees of freedom have been integrated out. The properties of this free action can in principle be derived from a microscopic theory of the constituent particles. One can turn the argument around and ask what hints a free field action would point to a bound state. This is a more difficult question to which we at least partially come back further below.

³E.g., the combined term with λ and λ^\dagger can be written as

$$\text{Tr}' \lambda^\dagger G_1 \frac{1}{1 - \Lambda_{\text{SP}} G_2 \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger G_1} \lambda G_2 \frac{1}{1 - \Lambda_{\text{SP}}^\dagger G_1 \Lambda_{\text{SP}} G_2}. \quad (12)$$

Similar expressions hold for the $\lambda^\dagger \lambda^\dagger$ and $\lambda \lambda$ terms.

The non-relativistic theory. In this general outline of the method I will only consider simple examples for illustration, starting with the non-relativistic theory. Consider two non-relativistic spin-less particles with Hamiltonians $H_j = p_j^2/2m_j$, $j = 1, 2$. This could be a Hydrogen atom with a proton and an electron. For simplicity I disregard spin-effects.

Performing the steps described above yields

$$S_{\text{eff}} = \text{Tr} Q^* [-V] Q + \text{Tr} \{ Q^* \Lambda + \Lambda^* Q \} - i \text{Tr} \ln \{ \mathbb{1} - G_1 \Lambda G_2^* \Lambda^* \} , \quad (14)$$

where $G_j = [i\partial_t - H_j]^{-1}$ and $-G_2(-x) =: G_2^*(x)$. If we look at the low-density limit (far from condensation), we can expand the logarithm to lowest order. Integrating out the Λ fields I obtain $S_{\text{eff}} = \text{Tr} \{ Q^* [\mathcal{G}_0^{-1} - V] Q \}$, where (for two time arguments) $\mathcal{G}_0^{-1} = (iG_p G_e^*)^{-1}$. I have not been specific about whether one or two time arguments have been used. If two have been used, one can follow the treatment shown in [5] for instantaneous interactions, or rather a very much simplified version of it. Having started with one time argument, one can use the product rule to show that $\mathcal{G}_0^{-1} = i\partial_t - H_1 - H_2$ holds.⁴ In center-of-mass coordinates $\mathbf{X} = (m_1 \mathbf{x} + m_2 \mathbf{y})/M$ with $M = m_1 + m_2$ and $\boldsymbol{\xi} = \mathbf{y} - \mathbf{x}$ we can write the SPE (defining $\tilde{Q}(\mathbf{X}, \boldsymbol{\xi}) := Q(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2)$) as

$$i\partial_t \tilde{Q}(\mathbf{X}, \boldsymbol{\xi}, t) = \left(\frac{\mathbf{P}^2}{2M} + \frac{\mathbf{p}^2}{2\mu} + V(\boldsymbol{\xi}) \right) \tilde{Q}(\mathbf{X}, \boldsymbol{\xi}, t) \quad (15)$$

with momentum operators are $\mathbf{P} = -i\nabla_{\mathbf{X}}$, $\mathbf{p} = -i\nabla_{\boldsymbol{\xi}}$, and $\mu = m_1 m_2 / M$. The second order expansion is

$$S_{2,\text{eff}}[q^\dagger, q] = \text{Tr} \left\{ q^\dagger [i\partial_t - H_X(\mathbf{P}) - H_\xi(\hat{\mathbf{p}}) - V(\boldsymbol{\xi})] q \right\} \quad (16)$$

with $\hat{\mathbf{p}} = -i\nabla$. Expand the field q in bound state eigenfunctions of the Hamiltonian $H_\xi(\hat{\mathbf{p}}) + V(\boldsymbol{\xi})$ as

$$q(X, x) = \sum_n \chi_n(\mathbf{X}, t) \varphi_n(\boldsymbol{\xi}) . \quad (17)$$

The action then simplifies into a sum of single compound particle actions

$$S_{2,\text{eff}}[\chi^\dagger, \chi] = \sum_n \text{Tr} \left\{ \chi_n^\dagger \left[i\partial_t - H_X^{(n)}(\mathbf{P}) - E_n \right] \chi_n \right\} , \quad (18)$$

⁴Note that Q is a slightly different object for the equal-time approach than with different times. Essentially, the Q definitions differ by a time integration. One has to pick either of the approaches from the beginning and has to be careful with the physical dimensions.

where $H_X^{(n)}(\mathbf{P}) = \text{Tr} \varphi_n^\dagger H_X(\mathbf{P}) \varphi_n$. There may be bilinear coupling terms if $\text{Tr} \varphi_n^\dagger H_X(\mathbf{P}) \varphi_{n'}$ does not vanish. Then, further diagonalization is needed, but eventually the result is a theory of different particles characterized by the set of eigenstates.

The main point of this exercise is to show that an action for the composite system arises. It appears as a single-particle action (for each eigenstate related to the inner degrees of freedom) as long as excitations can be neglected. This picture breaks down if the composite becomes highly excited. Then the expansion of the logarithm has to be taken into account. Furthermore, radiative corrections come into play. In a thermodynamic treatment we expect occupation of the lowest energy states, while higher energy states are unstable, decaying into the lower energy states if the transition is allowed. This can be by radiating off photons, but if the gas becomes denser, there are also non-radiative transitions. (In reality, molecules form, which the framework would also allow to treat.) In fact, the next term of the logarithm yields a Λ^3 term. At the saddle point Λ and Q are related via the first equation in (8). This then translates into a non-linear Schroedinger equation

$$i\partial_t Q = (H_1 + H_2 + V) Q + g|Q|^2 Q, \quad (19)$$

where g is determined from the action.

Another point to consider is that in atomic systems the bound states coexist with the dissociated components. Chemical reactions occur in both directions and the unbound and bound states are in thermal equilibrium. If we repeated the steps above in a finite temperature representation, we would not integrate out the single particle fields completely. Instead, we would keep an action like Eq. (5). In this action, there are interaction terms $\text{Tr} \{ \psi_1^T \Lambda^\dagger \psi_2 \}$ and $\text{Tr} \{ \psi_2^\dagger \Lambda \psi_1^* \}$, which describe how the components bind into or dissociate from the composite fields. The component particle numbers are not conserved independently, but have to be counted together with the bound states.

In the low energy and long range limit in which the inner degrees of freedom of the bound state are not resolved, $\Lambda^\dagger(x, x')$ can be approximated by $\Phi(x)\delta(x - x')$. The interaction becomes

$$\text{Tr} \left\{ \psi_1^T(x) \Lambda^\dagger(x, x') \psi_2(x') \right\} \rightarrow \text{Tr} \left\{ \psi_1^T(x) \Phi(x) \psi_2(x) \right\}. \quad (20)$$

This is an approximate Yukawa-like coupling between the component fields and the composite field. If energy levels are raised to a scale where the

binding length is resolved, the approximation breaks down. It is interesting to contemplate whether this is a mechanism for Yukawa couplings; however, one should emphasize that it is restricted to interactions between composites and their components. Note that different eigenstates of the bound system will yield different coupling strengths.

Interpretation of the non-linearity using the example of BCS superconductivity. The BCS theory of superconductivity [7] allows to illustrate the effect of the logarithmic term in the action. Consider electrons $\psi_\uparrow, \psi_\downarrow$ near the Fermi surface and an interaction

$$\text{Tr} \{ \bar{\psi}_\uparrow(y) \bar{\psi}_\downarrow(x) g(x-y) \psi_\downarrow(x) \psi_\uparrow(y) \} , \quad (21)$$

which is attractive in a momentum range close to the Fermi surface. The interaction g is defined positive for attractive forces. The spin index makes the particles distinguishable. Now integrate out the fermion fields in the Gaussian action

$$\text{Tr} \left(\begin{array}{cc} \bar{\psi}_\uparrow & \psi_\downarrow \end{array} \right) \left(\begin{array}{cc} G^{-1} & \Lambda \\ \Lambda^* & -\overleftarrow{G}^{-1} \end{array} \right) \left(\begin{array}{c} \psi_\uparrow \\ \bar{\psi}_\downarrow \end{array} \right) , \quad (22)$$

where $-\overleftarrow{G}^{-1} = G_h^{-1}$, introducing the hole Green function G_h [8]. Structurally, a finite Λ saddle point acts like a mass. We arrive at the action (Q 's integrated out)

$$S_{\text{eff}}[\Lambda^*, \Lambda] = \text{Tr} \{ \Lambda^* g^{-1} \Lambda - i \ln [\mathbb{1} - \Lambda^* G \Lambda G_h] \} . \quad (23)$$

This action (with Q 's integrated out and the discrete eigenstate disregarded) is essentially the action obtained in the treatment of the BCS theory via the path integral field theory approach [8]. Although $\Lambda(x, x')$ is a function of two arguments, we can look at the limit $\Lambda(x, x') \rightarrow \Delta$. Like in BCS theory, we reduce g to a constant interaction within the given momentum range close to the Fermi surface. Then, in complete analogy to path integral derivations described in text books (e.g., [8]), the SPE becomes the well-known gap equation $g^{-1} = \text{Tr}[\omega_n^2 + \xi_p^2 + |\Delta|^2]^{-1}$ with Matsubara frequency ω_n . Further, $\xi_p = \epsilon_p - \mu$ is the energy difference with respect to the Fermi level.

From this the conclusion is that the non-linear terms can induce condensation of the bound states. For systems far away from condensation (e.g., at high temperatures for thermal phase transitions), the higher order terms should be negligible. Then, the equation for the bound states becomes the BSE in ladder approximation.

An obvious question to ask is whether this example relates the bound state theory with the well-known soft mass mechanisms as described, e.g., in [9]. I shortly touch this topic with the following.

A relativistic example. The formally simplest possible relativistic system is a pair of Weyl fermions and I will investigate what formally happens if I assume that bound states of them exist. (BCS theory indicates that fermions with a linear dispersion relation can be bound.) The massless limit of the Dirac equation in Weyl representation is equivalent to the Weyl equations

$$[i\partial_t \pm \boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{p}] u_{\pm} = 0 \quad (24)$$

with $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ being the vector of the three Pauli matrices. Mass terms in the Dirac equation are coupling terms between u_+ and u_- . Postulating an interaction that creates such a coupling, we can identify Q with $u_-^\dagger u_+$ or its Hermitian conjugate and introduce the Λ fields. The fermion kernel then takes the form

$$\begin{pmatrix} i\partial_t + \boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{p} & -\Lambda^\dagger \\ -\Lambda & i\partial_t - \boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{p} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (25)$$

which resembles the Dirac equation in Weyl representation, but the non-diagonal elements are fields, not constants. Here, Λ in general is a matrix, which might have non-diagonal terms. Further, Λ has two space arguments. Note the coupling $u_+^\dagger \Lambda^\dagger u_- + u_-^\dagger \Lambda u_+$ that is automatically created, when introducing Λ and deriving Eq. (5). In the long range limit it again takes a form of a Yukawa-like coupling.⁵ Integrating out the fermions, the effective action for the bound states reads

$$\mathcal{S}_{\text{eff}} = -\text{Tr} \left\{ Q^\dagger U Q \right\} + \text{Tr} \left\{ Q^\dagger \Lambda + \Lambda^\dagger Q \right\} - i \text{Tr} \ln \left\{ \mathbb{1} - G_+ \Lambda^\dagger G_- \Lambda \right\}, \quad (26)$$

where Q and Λ are bosonic fields. The logarithmic term in the action yields a potential for these fields, which makes condensation possible in principle.⁶

⁵One might contemplate whether there is any relationship with Yukawa-like couplings in the standard model. However, despite the formal possibility and the additional benefit of a potential term in the action, the fact that one particle (spin-0 boson) has several Yukawa couplings with other particles does not fit into this simple picture. Nevertheless, it might be interesting to ask whether the framework might be useful for composite Higgs models [10].

⁶By that I mean that, e.g., after integrating out Λ , the structure of the equation is just like in the BCS example. Then, if the binding force has the right properties, the saddle point equation yields a gap equation. Put differently, if U^{-1} is a differential operator (like, e.g., the d'Alembert operator) multiplied by a coupling constant, then we have a free action plus a potential term with second, fourth, and higher orders, which in principle can take the shape of a Mexican hat potential.

However, this is a purely formal statement and the physical consequences have not been worked out here.

Summary. Existing techniques from many-particle theory allow to derive an action for a composite system. The saddle point approximation yields an equation that can be brought in relation with the Bethe-Salpeter equation. Additional non-linear terms describe condensation of the composites. The coexistence of bound and unbound states results in an interaction between them. In the limit, where the inner degrees of freedoms are not excited, this interaction takes a Yukawa-like form. The trace-log in the action can lead to a symmetry breaking potential. The next steps would be the application to explicit physical and possibly chemical systems.

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